

Film Industry competitiveness dashboard– *Appendix*

Project: Reviving, Boosting, Optimising and Transforming European Film Competitiveness - REBOOT

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CONTENT

- 1.1. EFI Competitive Conditions (Firm Strategy, Structure and Rivalry): contents and data visualization 9
- 1.2. EFI background: factor conditions: contents and data visualization 11
- 1.3. EFI Audience (Demand Conditions): contents and data visualization 14
- 1.4. EFI Ecology (Related and Supporting Industries): contents and data visualization.. 17

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Figures

Figure 1 - Main dashboard interface	6
Figure 2 – Overview of EFI Framework – Introduction Panel	6
Figure 3 – EFI Competitive Conditions (Firm Strategy, Structure and Rivalry) - Domain Panel	7
Figure 4 – EFI Background (Factor Conditions) - Domain Panel	7
Figure 5 – EFI Audience (Demand Conditions) - Domain Panel.....	8
Figure 6 – EFI Ecology (Related and Supporting Industries) - Domain Panel	8
Figure 7a – International Agreements of the EFI	9
Figure 7b – International Market of the EFI.....	9
Figure 7c – The economic performance of the EFI vis-à-vis the rest of the economy.....	10
Figure 8a - The Historical Perspective of the EFI.....	0
Figure 8b - Governance and Public Value of the EFI	0
Figure 8c - The Perspective of EFI Creators	0
Figure 8d - EFI Legal Mapping	0
Figure 8e - Mapping of Institutional Actors and Policy Models	13
Figure 9a - Film Preferences of Young Audiences	0
Figure 9b - Analysis of Young Audience Awards.....	0
Figure 9c - European Films' Contents and Association with UN SDGs	15
Figure 9d - European Films in Key EU Markets	0
Figure 10 - The EFI Inter-sectoral Network: Sectoral Embeddedness	17

Tables

Table 1 - - List of deliverables that are currently populating the competitiveness dashboard 18

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APPENDIX OF THE CONTENTS OF THE REBOOT COMPETITIVENESS DASHBOARD WEBSITE

This document serves as an appendix to Deliverable 6.1 – Film Industry Competitiveness Dashboard of the REBOOT project. It provides a visual documentation of the contents embedded in the REBOOT Competitiveness Dashboard, which is grounded in Porter's Diamond Model and was developed under Deliverable 6.1, accessible at: <https://thereboot-project.eu/dashboard>.

The Dashboard consolidates the key findings and research outputs produced across the REBOOT project. The present document illustrates the interface elements, represented as figures, within each accessible web tab, capturing the default view displayed upon first access to each section. Each figure is accompanied by a brief descriptive caption, which also serves as a navigational guide for users.

For further information regarding the project deliverables, please refer to the table below or consult Report D6.1 – Film Industry Competitiveness Dashboard directly.

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Figure 1 - Main dashboard interface

The dashboard displays a circular diagram representing the EFI (Ecosystem Framework for Innovation) model, divided into four segments: EFI Competitive Conditions (Firm Strategy, Structure and Rivalry), EFI Background (Factor Conditions), EFI Audience (Demand Conditions), and EFI Ecology (Related and Supporting Industries). The "EFI" label is centered within the wheel, providing an overview of the framework's key dimensions.

Figure 2 – Overview of EFI Framework – Introduction Panel

The dashboard's introduction panel provides a theoretical overview of the EFI framework, outlining its four key dimensions: EFI Competitive Conditions (Firm Strategy, Structure and Rivalry), EFI Background (Factor Conditions), EFI Audience (Demand Conditions), and EFI Ecology (Related and Supporting Industries); each corresponding to one of Porter's Diamond Model determinants.

Figure 3 – EFI Competitive Conditions (Firm Strategy, Structure and Rivalry) - Domain Panel

The domain panel for EFI Competitive Conditions (Firm Strategy, Structure and Rivalry) lists of three accessible contents covering key results from REBOOT project.

Figure 4 – EFI Background (Factor Conditions) - Domain Panel

The domain panel for EFI Background (Factor Conditions) lists five accessible contents covering key results from REBOOT project.

Figure 5 – EFI Audience (Demand Conditions) - Domain Panel

The domain panel for Audience (Demand Conditions) lists four accessible contents covering key results from REBOOT project.

Figure 6 – EFI Ecology (Related and Supporting Industries) - Domain Panel

The domain panel for Audience (Demand Conditions) one accessible content covering key results from REBOOT project.

1.1. EFI COMPETITIVE CONDITIONS (FIRM STRATEGY, STRUCTURE AND RIVALRY): CONTENTS AND DATA VISUALIZATION

Figure 7a – International Agreements of the EFI

Figure 7b – International Market of the EFI

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Figure 7c – The economic performance of the EFI vis-à-vis the rest of the economy

The domain panel for EFI Competitive Conditions offers three complementary layers of analysis.

- Figure 7a presents the "International Agreements of the EFI" report, displaying a filterable table of EU agreements with third countries (e.g., association, trade, cultural cooperation, and strategic partnership agreements) organised by country signatory and year.
- Figure 7b illustrates the "International Market of the EFI" report, summarising a large-scale survey conducted between November 2024 and February 2025 across 432 participants from over 25 European nationalities, structured into expandable thematic sections covering demographic information, EFI identity, perceptions of competitiveness, international market, and VOD platforms.
- Figure 7c shows the data visualizer of "The economic performance of the EFI vis-à-vis the rest of the economy", enabling cross-country comparison of economic indicators (such as total wages in the EFI vis-à-vis manufacturing) with interactive filters for metrics, countries, and reference year, and an export-to-PDF option.

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1.2. EFI BACKGROUND: FACTOR CONDITIONS: CONTENTS AND DATA VISUALIZATION

Figure 8a - The Historical Perspective of the EFI

The historical perspective of the EFI

This section presents six recurring tensions and paradoxes that characterize the last three decades of the European Film Industry. The quotes that illustrate their complexity have been selected from the report Lessons from the past (link below), which reflects how senior professionals look back at these transformations.

Key paradoxes in the European Film Industry

01. Overproduction	02. Hollywood Dominance
03. Impact of Streaming Platforms	04. Cinema's Survival / End vs. Resilience
05. European Policy Goals / Diversity vs. Competitiveness	06. Changing Role of Producers

Note: The case study of Flanders and Spain [...]

Overproduction

- Overproduction is seen as a weakness, particularly in relation to European cinema's lack of competitiveness. However, it can also be viewed as a sign of Europe's cultural and linguistic diversity.
- While widely acknowledged, overproduction is often considered a sensitive topic, as it raises uncomfortable questions about which films should not be made.

Quotes Show quotes

Hollywood Dominance

- Hollywood's dominance is acknowledged as a historical and structural challenge, yet European cinema has been generally praised for its diversity and distinctiveness.
- While the trope of Hollywood dominance has often been problematized in negative terms, most interviewees—especially in the production and exhibition sectors—discussed these matters in a less critical tone and emphasised Hollywood's power to attract audiences. Many stakeholders highlighted the resilience of European cinema and the opportunities presented by US competitors, while others underlined the need for stronger European players to counterbalance Hollywood's dominance.

Quotes Show quotes

Impact of Streaming Platforms

- Opportunities vs. challenges: streaming platforms have brought significant financial investments and international visibility to European cinema but have also

Figure 8b - Governance and Public Value of the EFI

Governance and Public Value of the EFI

Key findings with quotes that complement the findings

- Public-value thinking is still fragmented across Europe** - the six country case studies show that "government support for public value in the film industry remains fragmented and lacks cohesive coordination" (the lack of a unified strategy limits the ability to leverage public funds for maximum cultural impact).
- Competitiveness must be re-defined beyond pure economics** - the panel stresses that "competitiveness should also consider how well a film connects with its community and reflects public questioning," highlighting that cultural relevance and social impact are essential metrics of a film sector's strength.
- Measuring public value is complex despite some quantifiable actions** - Elke Jelladeu, the General Director of the Thessaloniki Film Festival, points out that "while these actions are measurable, assessing their impact on public values remains complex," indicating that current metrics (e.g., numbers of training programmes, audience counts) capture activity but not the deeper societal effects.
- Policy gaps hinder the translation of public value objectives into practice** - interviews reveal that "government support for public value ... is fragmented and lacks cohesive coordination", and that "the process of crafting film policies is often influenced by local political dynamics," which hampers consistent implementation of cultural value goals.
- Targeted funding incentives can reinforce public value outcomes** - the Austrian case illustrates that public funding "includes gender- and environmental- bonuses to promote inclusivity and sustainability," showing how specific policy levers can embed public-value criteria into financial support mechanisms.

Related policy implications

- Integrate governance** - create a EU-level coordination body to align national funding streams and ensure that public-value objectives are uniformly applied.
- Develop metrics** - adopt mixed-method indicators (e.g., cultural-participation rates, education programmes, diversity targets) to move beyond pure economic KPIs.
- Standardise grant-evaluation** - include mandatory public-value impact assessments while preserving flexible tax-rebate schemes.

Quantitative findings

Table - Quantitative findings

Indicator	Figure
Public-funding share of an average European film budget	~ 42% of total budget
Change in public-funding share (2016-2020)	39% → 41.8%
Direct public-funding contribution to European theatrical-fiction films	26% of total financing
Broadcaster (public-service) contribution to the same	21% of total financing

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Figure 8c - The Perspective of EFI Creators

Figure 8d - EFI Legal Mapping

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Figure 8e - Mapping of Institutional Actors and Policy Mo

The domain panel for EFI Background (Factor Conditions) provides five complementary results from the REBOOT project.

- Figure 8a presents "The Historical Perspective of the EFI," identifying six key paradoxes characterising the last three decades of the European Film Industry, supported by quotes from industry professionals.
- Figure 8b illustrates the "Governance and Public Value of the EFI", presenting key findings on public funding fragmentation, competitiveness metrics, policy gaps, and targeted funding incentives, complemented by quantitative indicators and related policy implications.
- Figure 8c shows "The Perspective of EFI Creators", highlighting gender representation gaps, uneven policy frameworks across countries, and youth and diaspora support disparities, alongside key quantitative indicators and policy recommendations.
- Figure 8d displays the "EFI Legal Mapping", offering a multi-level overview of the legal norms regulating filmmaking in the EU, organised by country and filterable across thematic sheets such as cultural diversity, copyright, and protection of minors.
- Figure 8e presents the "Mapping of Institutional Actors and Policy Models", providing an overview of the promotion of the EFI at the international level, structured into expandable sections covering funding schemes, VoD platforms, and bilateral and multilateral funding mechanisms across EU Member States.

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1.3. EFI AUDIENCE (DEMAND CONDITIONS): CONTENTS AND DATA VISUALIZATION

Figure 9a - Film Preferences of Young Audiences

Figure 9b - Analysis of Young Audience Awards

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Figure 9c - European Films' Contents and Association with UN SDGs

Figure 9d - European Films in Key EU Markets

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The domain panel for *EFI Audience (Demand Conditions)* provides four complementary reports.

- Figure 9a presents "Film Preferences of Young Audiences," structured into expandable sections covering viewing habits, cinema attendance, genre preferences, and country-of-origin rankings among young Europeans.
- Figure 9b illustrates the "Analysis of Young Audience Awards", examining the preferences of 12–14-year-old cinema audiences in Europe through the ranking and admissions data of Young Audience Award-winning films.
- Figure 9c displays "European Films' Contents and Association with UN SDGs," mapping European film productions to the 17 UN Sustainable Development Goals, filterable by SDG theme and co-production type.
- Figure 9d presents "European Films in Key EU Markets," providing a dataset of the top-performing European films across selected EU Member States, including admissions, awards, IMDb ratings, and worldwide gross revenue.

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1.4. EFI ECOLOGY (RELATED AND SUPPORTING INDUSTRIES): CONTENTS AND DATA VISUALIZATION

Figure 10 - The EFI Inter-sectoral Network: Sectoral Embeddedness

Figure 10 presents "The EFI Inter-sectoral Network: Sectoral Embeddedness," an interactive map visualising the degree of embeddedness of the European Film Industry across EU countries, filterable by year (2016 or 2019) and by index type, including embeddedness indices for the film industry, manufacturing, and tourism

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Table 1 -- List of deliverables that are currently populating the competitiveness dashboard

Deliverables/elements	Partner/Author(s)	Title description	Type of data	Porter's Diamond Model Dashboard forces/domain	DOI/link/reference
D2.4	UGENT	Key paradoxes in the European Film Industry over the past three decades;	Qualitative data	Factor condition	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14765810
D3.2	UNIVIE	Governance and Public Value Report	Qualitative data	Factor condition	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13865245
D3.4	UNIVIE	Recommendations on innovation for European film creators	Mixed	Factor condition	https://zenodo.org/records/15309331
D3.6 - T3.1	ELIAMEP-SSSA	The institutional context of the EU film industry (Part 1)	Qualitative data	Factor condition	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16639434
D3.6-T3.4(a)	ELIAMEP-UNIVIE	The institutional context of the EU film industry (Part 2(a))	Qualitative data	Factor condition	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16639434
D3.6-T3.4(b)	ELIAMEP-UNIVIE	The institutional context of the EU film industry (Part 2(b))	Quantitative data	Demand Condition	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16639434
D3.6 - T3.5	ELIAMEP	The institutional context of the (Part 3)	Qualitative data	Firm strategy, structure and rivalry	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16639434
D4.1	ULIEGE	"International Market" in the European Film Industry	Mixed	Firm strategy, structure and rivalry	https://zenodo.org/records/15970684
D5.2	JYU	Analysis of the awarded films (Data and ranking)	Mixed	Demand Condition	https://thereboot-project.eu/pdfs/research-001.pdf
D6.1-T6.1.1(a)	SSSA	The economic indicators of the EFI	Quantitative data	Firm strategy, structure and rivalry	https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e50d34cb21&appId=PPGMS
D6.1-T6.1.1(b)	SSSA	The Sectoral Embeddedness of the EFI	Quantitative data	Related and Supporting Industries	https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e50d34cb21&appId=PPGMS
D6.1-T6.1.2	SSSA	Analysis on European films' contents using the UN-Sustainable Development Goals framework	Quantitative data	Demand Conditions	https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e50d34cb21&appId=PPGMS

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